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Rustamova Shahnoza Omonovna

Chief accountant of "DYNINNO TAS INTERNATIONAL" LLC

CULTURAL VALUES AS A FACTOR DETERMINING THE PENSION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

In the article the close relationship between socio-culture values and socio-economic development of the country is empirically discussed. Through the analyzing the depth of social values of uzbek nation and its impact on economical situation of the state in the article the reflection of specifics of social values system of uzbek nation into pension system by several factors is stated.

Keywords: Pension system, pension supply, demographic and economics factors, social protection of the elderly; cultural values.

Рустамова Шахноза Омоновна

"DYNINNO TAS INTERNATIONAL" МЧЖ бош ҳисобчиси

**МАДАНИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАР ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ПЕНСИЯ ТИЗИМИНИ
БЕЛГИЛОВЧИ ОМИЛИ СИФАТИДА****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Мақолада маданий қадриятлар ва халқлар ривожланишининг ижтимоий-иқтисодий кўрсаткичлари ўртасидаги чамбарчас боғлиқликни эмпирик тарзда кўрсатилган. Ўзбек миллатининг ижтимоий қадриятлари чуқурлиги ва унинг мамлакат иқтисодий тузилишига таъсирини таҳлил қилган ҳолда, Ўзбекистон жамиятидаги қадриятлар тизимининг ўзига хослигини мамлакат пенсия тизимида ўз ифодасини топиши бир қатор омиллар орқали мақолада баён этилган.

Калит сўзлар: Пенсия тизими, пенсия таъминоти, демографик ва иқтисодий омиллар, кексаларни ижтимоий ҳимоя қилиш, маданий қадриятлар.

Рустамова Шахноза Омоновна

Главный бухгалтер ООО "DYNINNO TAS INTERNATIONAL".

КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ ЦЕННОСТИ ОПРЕДЕЛЯЮЩИЙ ФАКТОР ПЕНСИОННУЮ СИСТЕМУ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье эмпирически рассматриваются тесная связь культурных ценностей и социально-экономические показатели развития стран. Посредством анализа глубины социальных ценностей узбекского народа и его влияния на экономический уклад страны в статье излагается своеобразная система социальных ценностей узбекского народа, отражающаяся в пенсионной системе через ряд факторов.

Ключевые слова: Пенсионная система, пенсионное обеспечение, демографические и экономические факторы, социальная защита пожилых людей, культурные ценности.

Introduction

The connection between the socio-economic life of the population of Uzbekistan and its socio-cultural values is studied in a narrow scope, but at the same time, this topic is relevant, both from the point of view of economic growth and the spiritual and moral development of the nation as a whole. Uzbekistan is in the stage of full-fledged transformation into a market model of economic development and broad economic integration into the world community. The qualitative completion of these processes and the achievement of prospective economic growth presupposes taking into account the specifics of the country, which is manifested in the socio-political-economic-historical development of the region through the prism of the socio-cultural values of the people.

The current stage of the country's development is pushing for large-scale and deep-sectoral systemic reforms. The necessary reform measures are being taken by the current government of the country, and it is reflected in the ongoing turbulent transformation processes.

In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a meeting on November 21, 2019 to discuss priorities in the field of social protection noted the transition to a three-tier pension system. [1]

At the heart of these changes is the fact that the current pension system is not fully justified, and these shortcomings in the system are due not only to the transition to international standards, but also to the weak position of the population against the negative performance of the system. Because the current pension system in Uzbekistan is based on the solidarity of generations, in which the fund for pension payments is formed by the economically active population not of retirement age through a single social payment. That is, those who have not reached retirement age make pension payments for those of retirement age. There is no doubt that this system will be in crisis, but why is this system still not severely criticized in Uzbekistan? To understand the fundamentals of such a problematic and enduring economic mechanism, it is necessary to look at the social values of the Uzbek nation.

Literature review

Contemporary research by economists, sociologists and political scientists is drawing the attention of the scientific community to the role played by certain cultural, social and socio-psychological factors in ensuring the well-being of society and determining the economic behavior of people (Altman, 2001, 379–391; Dayton-Johnson, 2001; Fukuyama, 1999; Inglehart, 2000, 80–97).

According to many authoritative foreign experts, culture matters and has an impact on socio-economic development. A number of theoretical and empirical approaches have been proposed in cross-cultural psychology and related sciences to measure cultural differences and their links to socioeconomic development (Hofstede, 2001; Inglehart, 1997; Leung and Bond, 2004, 119–197; Schwartz, 2004, 3–73).

According to Kasimova (2017), the financial instability of pension funds in the pension system based on the "Principle of Solidarity of Generations", the need to increase payments to the pension fund increases, and the need to allocate transfers from the budget arises.

Analysis and results

Of course, such a phenomenon exists at different levels in all countries of the world and is directly related to countries' social values. According to many reputable foreign experts, culture matters and influences socio-economic development.

The relationship of the economy with cultural values was reflected in the issues that were raised during the International Harvard Symposium "Cultural Values and the Progress of Humanity" held in April 1999 at the American Academy of Arts and Sciences in Cambridge, USA, which was attended by leading economists, sociologists, political scientists and cultural anthropologists of the world. The materials of this symposium were published in the book "Culture matters". Some of the questions can be summarized as follows: [2]

1. The globalization of humanity brings cultures closer together or do cultures remain unchanged despite the assimilation of technologies, styles of clothing, food and everyday behavior? What changes and what remains unchanged?

2. Are shifts in cultural values necessary for the economy to develop in a proactive way? And if so, in which direction?

3. How universal are cultural values and economic laws, what is their specificity in a particular geographic, political or ethnic environment?

4. Does this cultural specificity of transformation lend itself to economic and political development, under the influence of the processes of globalization?

Of course, no one can give exhaustive answers to these questions and this is not the purpose of this work, but the peculiarity of this period of human development lies in the fact that it poses such questions to modern science.

Many outstanding economists are well aware of the limitations of rational thinking and human behavior, realizing that there is a whole layer of unconscious norms and rules of behavior governed by cultural values that permeate economic (and any other) relations.

It is believed that life and economic processes are subject to written laws and property rights. However, for most countries in the world, economic behavior is largely determined by unwritten codes, norms and conventions.

Numerous scientific studies are being conducted on the influence of cultural values on the economic development of nations. So, for example, the study by G. Hofstede revealed significant positive relationships between Individualism and the level of economic development, while with an increase in the level of well-being, Individualism acquires an inverse relationship with economic growth. [3]

According to R. Inglehart's measurements, it was revealed that the values of survival and traditional values are characteristic of poorer and less democratic countries, and the values of self-expression and secular-rational are characteristic of richer countries with more developed democracies. [4]

In S. Schwartz's measurements, economic development indicators are positively correlated with Autonomy and Equality and negatively - with Belonging (Conservatism) and Hierarchy. The level of democratization is positively correlated with Autonomy, Equality, Mastery and the level of national welfare. Autonomy, Equality and Harmony are associated with the absence of corruption, while Affiliation, Hierarchy and Mastery are positively associated with high corruption in society. [5]

In recent decades, along with economic and cultural factors, social factors that reflect the specifics of relationships between people in certain socio-economic conditions began to be considered as the most important for the development of society. In this regard, the concept of "social capital" began to be interpreted more broadly and often. [6]

Social capital is a tradition of social interaction that goes deep into history, which presupposes norms of reciprocity and trust between people, the widespread distribution of various kinds of voluntary associations and the involvement of citizens in politics in order to solve the problems facing the community. [7]

F. Fukuyama defines social capital as "a set of informal rules and norms shared by group members and allowing them to interact with each other. If group members expect their peers to behave in a reliable and honest manner, then they trust each other". [8]

Social capital is a kind of resource into which relations between participants in social interaction, characterized by mutual responsibility, as well as reliability and trust, are converted.

Like other forms of capital, social capital is productive. It contributes to the achievement of certain goals, which cannot be achieved in its absence. Social capital, along with other forms of capital, contributes to the well-being and competitiveness of a nation. Insufficiently high social capital does not allow building a full-fledged market society, even if the society has formally moved to a market economy.

When discussing the problem of social capital, the question arises about its components and indicators. The main one, or "core", is trust. Trust, being the main component of social capital, plays the role of a kind of "lubrication" of the "social mechanism" that allows a group or organization to function more efficiently, quickly and without interruptions. However, from our point of view, it is also necessary to take into account that reality (you can call it "social glue"), which holds the details of the "social mechanism" together. This role in public relations is played by civic identity. A common civic identity is of great importance for the economic development of society. [9]

Civic identity is an important factor performing an integration function in the process of economic development. How can the state of civic identity be assessed? Civic identity, like ethnic identity, has two important characteristics - certainty (the degree of clarity, clarity) and valence (the degree of positivity-negativity).

The certainty of group (civil, ethnic) identity is extremely important for a person as a social being. D. Taylor believes that the self-concept of personality is the most important construct for explaining the success or failure of various groups in society. At the same time, collective (civil, ethnic) identity is the central component of the self-concept of personality. The destruction of civic identity leads to collective demotivation, which is characterized by passivity, alienation from public life, and the absence of a long-term perspective. [10]

In addition to certainty, an important characteristic of civic identity is its valence (the degree of positivity-negativity). Positive civic identity improves social interaction. It promotes self-esteem of the individual, national pride, and hence the desire to work on the development of their country, which, without a doubt, is social capital. But perhaps most importantly, a positive civic identity unites and brings people together, which is perhaps the primary condition for a country's prosperity.

So, the social and economic development of countries depends not only on the availability of resources, technological advances and other purely economic and structural factors, but also on the cultural values that people living in certain countries share, on the level and quality of their social relationships and norms. regulating these relationships.

Research empirically proves a close connection between cultural values and socio-economic indicators of the development of nations. In modern social philosophy, the concept of value has different interpretations, but most often in the sense of "spirituality", "ideal", "morality". It is not for nothing that they say that national values are the wealth of society, a means that connects the past with the present and the future, a mighty force that educates a person to be spiritually mature and perfect.

Values are material and spiritual. They are manifested in the form of upbringing, customs and rituals. There are also such important values that are manifested in relationships, based on kindness, honesty, purity, sympathy, cooperation, and devotion.

In today's modern values science, national values are formed in an ethnic space that ensures the natural, historical, and social unity of people. It is said that it manifests itself in different ways, and affects people's minds and lifestyles in a unique way. It is also possible to learn national values from the way they are reflected in people's relationships and social activities, as well as from the spiritual basis for these attitudes, activities, goals, needs and aspirations.

For example, the values of personal achievement and success are found in many cultures, but at the same time they can be combined with other values that are unusual for the Western world. Confucianism at all times attached colossal importance to personal self-improvement and brought up an orientation towards achievement in children. Chinese children are taught how important it is to be successful.

The combination of obedience and striving for achievement predetermined the deeper goal of the socialization process in traditional China: the need for achievement should be fulfilled by humbly

fulfilling one's family role and remaining a dependent person. The balance between the desire for achievement and respect for elders is closely related to the mechanisms of trust and the dynamics of personal relationships that ensure the stability of social ties. This is evidenced by the high level of social capital that distinguishes modern China and which has a beneficial effect on the development of the economy and the modernization of society.

With the same analysis of the depth of the social values of the Uzbek nation and its impact on the economic structure of the country, it is possible to identify the specificity of value systems in the society of Uzbekistan, which is also reflected in the country's pension system.

Uzbekistan has taken its rightful place on the world stage not only thanks to its rich historical culture, for its contribution to world civilization or rich natural resources, but also for its highly moral spiritual and cultural values.

The system of values, which is an expression of the national values of the Uzbek people and their connection, was formed under the influence of the history of the nation, modern trends, various social and political processes. The national values here were formed in relation to the characteristics of the nation's origin and territorial space. Thus, as a result of the development of the unique and colorful values of the Uzbek nation, universal values were formed and developed.

National values by the nature does not stop at a narrow circle, but thrives, and is renewed in the process of life, and is enriched by the achievements of the values of other peoples. Obviously, each nation, ethnic group, tribe, or nation has its own traditions. The sense of universality is not only based on the desire to honor the values of one's own people, to show off, and to spread them among others, but also to accept and respect the values of each nation, people, and tribe as they are.

Respect for national and universal values, folk traditions and customs, corresponding to historical and national characteristics, developed interest in the national and cultural heritage, language, traditions and customs predetermines the social values of the Uzbek people.

The social values of any nation consist of the unity of national and universal values. National values are most often understood as a complex of socially significant material, spiritual, natural, religious, moral, philosophical and other assets, which is important not only for the past, but also has a positive impact on the present and future, inherent in the minds of people. This also includes social and spiritual phenomena that are significant for the development and independence of human society. [11]

National traditions that have been formed over hundreds of years now, together with cultural and spiritual values, accelerate development, contribute to the provision of a prosperous and free life of a person, and the achievement of spiritual and moral satisfaction.

The path of development of Uzbekistan is based on the unique way of life, conditions and characteristics of the people, national traditions and customs. The best customs, traditions, and spiritual heritage of the ancestors have been truly valued and have become a reality of social life.

The first President of Uzbekistan I. Karimov in his work said that "Our history is a great history. We have great traditions. The blood of our great ancestors, who made a significant contribution to world enlightenment, is flowing in our veins. This land was inhabited by great thinkers who taught the great values of goodness and humanity, peace and harmony, goodness and justice". [12]

The words of President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "In the implementation of our tasks, we will rely on our centuries-old traditions, rich spiritual heritage of our ancestors", prove that the values of the historical past, devotion to national traditions, respect for universal values are a priority area of government policy. [13]

The priceless spiritual wealth inherited from ancestors is the source of original values. Over the centuries, the noble qualities of the Uzbek people, such as high spirituality, justice, enlightenment, have become a kind of school of life for today's Uzbek youth.

The sources of spiritual thoughts created by the society run into ancient times. The peoples of Central Asia, which have a long and rich history, have created, improved their own valuable heritage and developed hundreds of generations in the spirit of such universal human qualities as humanism, patronage, friendship and mercy, hard work and generosity.

In particular, the immortal works of such geniuses as Khoja Ahmad Yassavi, Khoja Bahovaddin Naqshband, Imam al-Bukhari, Imam at Termizi, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Babur Mirzo – the rich past of Uzbekistan, original values and other national and spiritual wealth, not only the among people of religion, but also among secular scholars and the wider community is gaining its value.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the greatest spiritual blessing, the sacred religion of Islam, which is a fundamental element of the cultural integrity and social values of society, was revived. The system of national values formed in this country over the centuries has become intertwined with Islam and is one of the factors that determine its socio-economic life.

It is well known that every period of the ancient history of Uzbekistan is in harmony with religious values. Islam has always encouraged people to be self-governing, to multiply their good qualities and get rid of their bad ones. For centuries, religion has encouraged people to unite in the pursuit of the greatest goals.

The importance and place of Islam in the development of national values was so great that it enriched national values. In particular, the humanistic ideas brought about by Islam had a significant impact on the development of the spiritual values of the people. After the advent of Islam, the system of religious values in the life of the peoples of Central Asia was renewed, and many thinkers and encyclopedic scholars emerged from this land.

The ideas and instructions of Islam, which have become a national value, are inextricably linked with the natural and historical development of the nation, social life, lifestyle, past, future, culture, spirituality, customs, traditions, language, territory and so on. It manifested itself in various forms, in an integral relationship with national values, forming a unique system of national values. In this system, the values that ensure natural-historical unity - a single faith, kinship, harmony of older and younger generations, cultural and spiritual closeness, past and spiritual heritage, a sense of homeland, etc. are stable. [14]

Some Islamic values in the structure of national values have been formed in connection with the places of residence and living conditions of the people. The spiritual heritage, traditions, customs, literature, art of the Uzbek people and the forms of expression of universal values at the national level are associated with Islamic values. They are reflected in the cultural features and aspects that are passed down from generation to generation in the process of historical development of the Uzbek nation.

Today's youth and contemporaries can enjoy these spiritual treasures as much as they want. The value of social values is reflected in almost every Uzbek family, makhalla, in their weddings, funerals, holidays, khayit and hashar. In this way, the Uzbek public opinion is formed. This is the way of life of the Uzbek people, the way of thinking inherited from their ancestors. [15]

The set of common social values includes the preservation of peace and stability, socio-economic development, the promotion of human rights and freedoms, the upbringing of a new generation in a healthy and spiritually harmonious way. These priority social values require the integration and solidarity of all age groups in society. For this reason, the role of the family, community and the older generation in the social formation of the younger generation on the basis of national specific social values is high. [16]

Conclusion

From the above, we can conclude that the set of socio-cultural values formed in this region is so deep and social that it directly affects the socio-economic processes of the economic system.

In particular, if we single out the pension system under consideration, then the problems in this area and not solutions to these problems find their root precisely in the social values formed in the country. That is, the society of the Uzbek people since ancient times in a consensus in the mutual material support between the old and young generations, which is due to purely socio-cultural values established in the region historically and religiously.

An analysis should be carried out to identify the relationship of established cultural property to the legally approved terms and conditions of pension payments and fees. At the same time, it is necessary to clarify the position of the authors that they are in a consensus in their view of the existing

connection between national cultural values and the allegedly “without failure” pension system of the country.

Unfortunately, this relationship has negative consequences for the country's economy and the well-being of society as a whole. On the one hand, this connection smooths out and hides the problems of the system (which is good for legislators and regulators of the country's financial system) through non-resistance and acceptance by participants (both on the part of pension recipients and on the part of payers of pension contributions) of the pension system of the proposed conditions and legislative requirements.

On the other hand, there is a complete infringement of the rights of pensioners with their low pension payments and the rights of the economically active population with mandatory withdrawal of pension contributions (unified social payment to the state pension fund), which, in our opinion, is an abuse of society's values.

The dilemma is that the older generation (now pensioners) have the right to receive pension payments, since at one time they also paid pension contributions and thus provided the pension fund, but the question is how adequate is the amount of current pension payments. And also, the younger generation (now payers of the unified social payment) has the right to solve on a legislative basis issues related to the probability of life expectancy until retirement age: if the payer reaches retirement age, then what amount of pension will she/he receive, and in the case if she/he does not reach, then whether her/his possible pension payments will be compensated to her/his family and in what amount.

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6 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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